

O,O-Dialkyl-S-(4-substituted-phenyl-5-phenylacetamidothiazol-2-yl)phosphorothioates and O,O-Dialkyl-S-(4-substituted-phenyl-5-phenylthiazol-2-yl)phosphorothioate

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Syntheses of some O,O-dialkyl-S-(4-substituted-phenylacetamidothiazol-2-yl)phosphorothioates are described.

2-Chloroacetamido-4-substituted-phenyl-5-phenylthiazoles were condensed with potassium dialkyl phosphorothioates^{1,2} (KDTA) to obtain O,O-dialkyl-S-(4-substituted-phenyl-5-phenylacetamidothiazol-2-yl)phosphorothioates. 2-Mercapto-4-substituted-phenyl-5-phenylthiazoles were condensed with O,O-dialkyl thiophosphorochloridates^{3,4} (DTCL) to obtain O,O-dialkyl-S-(4-substituted-phenyl-5-phenylthiazol-2-yl)phosphorothioates. A series of new compounds were synthesised by condensing KDTA and DTCL with heterocyclic moieties. Most of the organo-phosphorus compounds have the general structure⁵,

Various heterocyclic moieties have been condensed with organophosphorus nucleus which are effective pesticides. In this paper R is CH₃, C₂H₅ and X is a thiazole nucleus joined via thioester linkage, viz. P-S-X. The title compounds were prepared according to Scheme 1.

Experimental

The following α -bromodeoxybenzoins⁶ were prepared: α -bromodeoxybenzoins (m.p. 55°), 4'-methyl- α -bromodeoxybenzoins (m.p. 87°), 4'-chloro- α -bromodeoxybenzoins (m.p. 67.5°) and 4'-methoxy- α -bromodeoxybenzoins (m.p. 72.5°). The following 2-amino-4-substituted-phenyl-5-phenylthiazoles⁷ were synthesised: 2-amino-4,5-diphenylthiazole (m.p. 185°), 2-amino-4-*p*-methylphenyl-5-phenylthiazole (m.p. 157°), 2-amino-4-*p*-chlorophenyl-5-phenylthiazole (m.p. 178°) and 2-amino-4-*p*-methoxyphenyl-5-phenylthiazole (m.p. 191°). The following 2-chloroacetamido-4-substituted-phenyl-5-phenylthiazoles⁸ were prepared: 2-chloroacetamido-4,5-diphenylthiazole (m.p. 126°), 2-chloroacetamido-4-*p*-methylphenyl-5-phenylthiazole (m.p. 135°), 2-chloroacetamido-4-*p*-chlorophenyl-5-phenylthiazole (m.p. 133°) and 2-chloroacetamido-4-*p*-methoxyphenyl-5-phenylthiazole (174°).

O,O-Dialkyl-S-(4-substituted-phenyl-5-phenylacetamidothiazol-2-yl)phosphorothioate. *General procedure*: 2-Chloroacetamido-4-substituted-phenyl-5-phenylthiazole (0.02 mol) and KDTA (0.02 mol) taken in dry acetone (30 cm³) were refluxed for 4 h and then cooled to room temperature. Solid potassium chloride was then removed by filtration. From the filtrate acetone was removed under reduced pressure and the resulting semi-solid product was dissolved in chloroform (25 cm³) and subjected to column chromatography using silica gel G column. The solvent of the eluate was evaporated under reduced pressure to give the product which was recrystallised from methanol.

The compounds thus prepared are described in Table 1.

2-Mercapto-4-substituted-phenyl-5-phenylthiazoles⁹: The following 2-mercapto-4-substituted-phenyl-5-phenylthiazoles⁹ were prepared: 2-mercapto-4,5-diphenylthiazole (m.p. 223°), 2-mercapto-4-*p*-methylphenyl-5-phenylthiazole (m.p. 203°), 2-mercapto-4-*p*-chlorophenyl-5-phenylthiazole (m.p. 230°) and 2-mercapto-4-*p*-methoxyphenyl-5-phenylthiazole (m.p. 207°).

TABLE 1—ANALYTICAL AND PHYSICAL DATA OF COMPOUNDS

Sl. no.	Compd.	M.p. °C	Appearance	Mol. formula	Analysis % : Found/(Calcd.)		
					C	H	N
1.	<i>O,O</i> -Dimethyl-5-(4,5-diphenyl acetamidothiazol-2-yl)phosphorothioate	115	White crystals	C ₁₉ H ₁₆ N ₂ O ₂ PS ₂	50.55 (50.65)	4.14 (4.25)	6.45 (6.22)
2.	<i>O,O</i> -Dimethyl-5-(4- <i>p</i> -methylphenyl-5-phenyl acetamidothiazol-2-yl)phosphorothioate	123	White crystals	C ₂₀ H ₂₁ N ₂ O ₂ PS ₂	51.63 (51.71)	4.99 (4.55)	5.91 (6.03)
3.	<i>O,O</i> -Dimethyl-5-(4- <i>p</i> -chlorophenyl-5-phenyl acetamidothiazol-2-yl)phosphorothioate	59	Off-white crystals	C ₁₉ H ₁₄ ClN ₂ O ₂ PS ₂	47.32 (47.05)	3.65 (3.74)	5.60 (5.77)
4.	<i>O,O</i> -Dimethyl-5-(4- <i>p</i> -methoxyphenyl-5-phenyl acetamidothiazol-2-yl)phosphorothioate	130	White crystals	C ₂₀ H ₂₁ N ₂ O ₄ PS ₂	50.23 (49.98)	4.24 (4.40)	5.56 (5.32)
5.	<i>O,O</i> -Diethyl-5-(4,5-diphenyl acetamidothiazol-2-yl)phosphorothioate	105	White shining crystals	C ₂₁ H ₂₂ N ₂ O ₂ PS ₂	52.58 (52.70)	4.75 (4.84)	6.01 (5.85)
6.	<i>O,O</i> -Diethyl-5-(4- <i>p</i> -methylphenyl-5-phenyl acetamidothiazol-2-yl)phosphorothioate	141	White crystals	C ₂₂ H ₂₃ N ₂ O ₂ PS ₂	53.81 (53.64)	5.01 (5.11)	5.61 (5.68)
7.	<i>O,O</i> -Diethyl-5-(4- <i>p</i> -chlorophenyl-5-phenyl acetamidothiazol-2-yl)phosphorothioate	111	White crystals	C ₂₁ H ₂₁ ClN ₂ O ₂ PS ₂	49.05 (49.17)	3.99 (4.32)	5.23 (5.46)
8.	<i>O,O</i> -Diethyl-5-(4- <i>p</i> -methoxyphenyl-5-phenyl acetamidothiazol-2-yl)phosphorothioate	118	Yellow crystals	C ₂₂ H ₂₃ N ₂ O ₄ PS ₂	51.74 (51.95)	4.56 (4.95)	5.83 (5.50)

TABLE 2—ANALYTICAL AND PHYSICAL DATA OF COMPOUNDS

Sl. no.	Compd.	M.p.	Appearance	Mol. formula	Analysis % : Found/(Calcd.)		
					O	H	N
1.	<i>O,O</i> -Dimethyl- <i>S</i> -(4,5-diphenylthiazol-2-yl)phosphorothioate	75	White crystals	C ₁₇ H ₁₄ NO ₂ PS ₂	51.75 (51.89)	4.20 (4.09)	3.33 (3.56)
2.	<i>O,O</i> -Dimethyl- <i>S</i> -(4- <i>p</i> -methylphenyl-5-phenylthiazol-2-yl)phosphorothioate	69	Light yellow	C ₁₈ H ₁₆ NO ₂ PS ₂	53.40 (53.05)	4.05 (4.45)	3.55 (3.43)
3.	<i>O,O</i> -Dimethyl- <i>S</i> -(4- <i>p</i> -chlorophenyl-5-phenylthiazol-2-yl)phosphorothioate	83	Creamish crystals	C ₁₇ H ₁₄ ClNO ₂ PS ₂	47.56 (47.71)	3.40 (3.53)	3.39 (3.27)
4.	<i>O,O</i> -Dimethyl- <i>S</i> -(4- <i>p</i> -methoxyphenyl-5-phenylthiazol-2-yl)phosphorothioate	76	Off-white needles	C ₁₈ H ₁₆ NO ₄ PS ₂	51.29 (51.05)	4.45 (4.28)	3.19 (3.30)
5.	<i>O,O</i> -Dimethyl- <i>S</i> -(4,5-diphenylthiazol-2-yl)phosphorothioate	53	Light brown crystals	C ₁₇ H ₁₄ NO ₂ PS ₂	53.98 (54.13)	4.50 (4.78)	3.50 (3.32)
6.	<i>O,O</i> -Dimethyl- <i>S</i> -(4- <i>p</i> -methylphenyl-5-phenylthiazol-2-yl)phosphorothioate	107	Creamish crystals	C ₂₀ H ₂₂ NO ₂ PS ₂	55.24 (55.15)	5.18 (5.09)	3.39 (3.21)
7.	<i>O,O</i> -Diethyl- <i>S</i> -(4- <i>p</i> -chlorophenyl-5-phenylthiazol-2-yl)phosphorothioate	103	Buff coloured crystals	C ₁₈ H ₁₆ ClNO ₂ PS ₂	50.25 (50.04)	4.30 (4.19)	2.93 (3.07)
8.	<i>O,O</i> -Dimethyl- <i>S</i> -(4- <i>p</i> -methoxyphenyl-5-phenylthiazol-2-yl)phosphorothioate	71	Link pink crystals	C ₂₀ H ₂₂ NO ₄ PS ₂	53.40 (53.19)	4.79 (4.91)	3.29 (3.10)

O,O-Dimethyl-*S*-(4-substituted-phenyl-5-phenylthiazol-2-yl)phosphorothioate : 2-Mercapto-4-substituted-phenyl-5-phenylthiazole (0.02 mol) was treated with sodium ethoxide (0.02 mol). Ethanol was removed by distillation and the sodium salt of thiazole was recovered as a gummy mass. To the sodium salt, dry acetone (30 cm³) was added and then DMTCL (3.2 g, 0.02 mol) was added dropwise. The mass was then refluxed for 4 h. It was cooled and sodium chloride was removed by filtration. From the filtrate acetone was distilled under reduced pressure. The resulting solid was purified by passing it through 90% activated silica and 10% alumina acidic column using chloroform as solvent. Chloroform was evaporated and the solid product was recrystallised from methanol (Table 2).

O,O-Diethylthiophosphorodithiocarbamate : To a suspension of ammonium dithiocarbamate¹⁰ (1.5 mol) in acetone (100 cm³) was added with vigorous

stirring *O,O*-diethylthiophosphorochloridate (0.1 mol) at room temperature for 2 h. The mixture was stirred overnight and then filtered. The filtrate was evaporated under reduced pressure and the residue was taken up in benzene (100 cm³) and washed with water (2 × 50 cm³). The benzene layer was dried with anhydrous sodium sulphate and was evaporated under reduced pressure. The oil obtained was *O,O*-diethylthiophosphorodithiocarbamate (85%).

O,O-Diethyl-5-(4-substituted-phenyl-5-phenylthiazol-2-yl)phosphorothioate : To α -bromosubstituted-deoxybenzoin (0.03 mol) dissolved in dry acetone (25 cm³) was added slowly *O,O*-diethylthiophosphorodithiocarbamate (7.2 g, 0.03 mol). The mixture was refluxed for 5 h on a water-bath and then cooled to room temperature. The resulting mass was transferred and cooled in an ice-bath when a

solid separated. It was filtered, dried and recrystallised twice from methanol (Table 2).

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References

1. E. I. HOEGBERG and J. T. CASSADAY, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1951, **73**, 557.
2. Indian Standards, 1978, 2669, 12.
3. A. R. H. LUTHER and A. V. CALVIN, *Chem. Abstr.*, 1952, **46**, 8319.
4. J. H. FLETCHER, J. C. HAMILTON, I. HECHENBLIENEER, E. I. HOEGBERG, B. J. SERTL and J. T. CASSADAY, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1950, **72**, 2461.
5. G. SCHRADER, "Die Entwicklung neuer Insektizide auf Grundlage organischer Fluor- und Phosphor Verbindungen", Monographia Nr. 62, *zy Angewandte Chemie und Chemie-Ingenieur-Technik*, Verlag Chemie, Weinheim, 1952.
6. G. DREYFAHL and H. GRAHMAR, *Chem. Abstr.*, 1958, **52**, 17177.
7. G. RUHLIG, *Chem. Ber.*, 1956, **89**, 107.
8. P. N. BHARGAVA, *Chem. Abstr.*, 1962 **57**, 16591.
9. J. RITTER and H. SOKOL, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1948, **70**, 3419.
10. H. GILMAN and A. H. BLATT, *Org. Synth.*, 1955, **3**, 768.